

DETERMINATION OF STRAIN AMPLIFICATION FACTORS FOR SIFT THEORY BASED ON RVE MODELS CONSIDERING PERIODICAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

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Keywords: Micromechanical modeling, Periodical boundary condition, Representative volume element, SIFT

ABSTRACT

Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT) is a micromechanics-based failure theory for multi-scale failure analysis of composite materials originally proposed by Gosse and Christensen (2001). One of the most special features of SIFT is that it can correlate the micromechanical strain in the fiber and matrix phase with the homogenized macroscopic strain at the lamina scale. In most cases, detailed finite element analysis of typical Representative Volume Element (RVE) can be carried out to establish the relationship between the micromechanical strain state within the fiber/matrix phase and the homogenized macroscopic strain at the lamina scale in form of strain amplification factors at several characteristic points within the RVE. However, previous researches always adopt typical RVE models with simplified displacement boundary conditions assuming that the RVE boundary lines keep still straight after deformation, which violate the boundary traction periodicity conditions and are over-constrained, also can not reflect the real deformation modes, therefore the precision of strain amplification factors may be reduced.

Actually, composite materials present obvious periodicity, which is also the foundation of RVE analysis. The deformation of single RVE extracted from composite material system will be affected by the neighboring RVEs, thus periodical boundary conditions should be applied to the RVE model to satisfy the displacement compatibility. In this paper, RVE finite element models considering periodical boundary conditions are developed for the execution of SIFT, for which the periodical boundary conditions are introduced through coupling equations of node pairs at corresponding positions in parallel faces. Consequently, more real deformation modes can be obtained and more precise strain within the RVE at the characteristic points can be extracted, then the more reasonable relationship between the micromechanical and macromechanical strain states can be established.

Finally, numerical examples are provided to illustrate the determination of strain amplification factors within the RVE considering periodical boundary conditions at the characteristic points.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been widely used in aerospace applications due to their various advantages compared with conventional light alloys, such as the higher strength and stiffness to weight

ratios, better damage tolerance, etc. Along with that, failure criteria and damage analysis methods for composite materials have always been hot research topics among several decades. Differing from metallic alloys, composite materials are multi-phase materials generally comprised of fibre phase and matrix phase with different mechanical properties; existing failure theories for composite materials including global stress and strain based ones which are generally regarded as “purely empirical”[1], and physics-based micromechanical ones which are acquiring more and more attention.

In reality, damage onset first appears at microscale in fiber phase or matrix phase or at the interface between fiber and matrix; the subsequent failure at lamina level and laminate level is the consequence of damage accumulation at microscale. To predict exactly the damage onset, it’s necessary to obtain the micromechanical response at fiber and matrix scale.

Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT) is a micromechanics-based failure theory for multi-scale failure analysis of composite materials originally proposed by Gosse and Christensen (2001)[2]. One of the most special features of SIFT is that it can correlate the micromechanical strain in the fiber and matrix phase with the homogenized macroscopic strain at the lamina scale. In most cases, detailed finite element analysis of typical Representative Volume Element (RVE) can be carried out to establish the relationship between the micromechanical strain state within the fiber/matrix phase and the homogenized macroscopic strain at the lamina scale in form of strain amplification factors at several characteristic points within the RVE. However, previous researches always adopt typical RVE models with simplified displacement boundary conditions assuming that the RVE boundary lines keep still straight after deformation[2-8], which violate the boundary traction periodicity conditions and are over-constrained, also can not reflect the real deformation modes, therefore the precision of strain amplification factors may be reduced.

Actually, composite materials present obvious periodicity, which is also the foundation of RVE analysis. The deformation of single RVE extracted from composite material system will be affected by the neighbouring RVEs, thus periodical boundary conditions should be applied to the RVE model to satisfy the displacement compatibility. In this paper, RVE finite element models considering periodical boundary conditions are developed for the execution of SIFT, for which the periodical boundary conditions are introduced through coupling equations of node pairs at corresponding positions in parallel faces. Consequently, more real deformation modes can be obtained and more precise strain within the RVE at the characteristic points can be extracted, then the more reasonable relationship between the micromechanical and macro mechanical strain states can be established.

2 STRAIN INVARIANT FAILURE THEORY

Most existing failure theories regard composite laminar as homogenised medium, the homogenised strain fields obtained from finite element analysis are usually used to evaluate failure. Actually, due to the mismatch of mechanical and thermal properties of fiber and matrix, the real strain and stress in fiber and matrix will be obviously amplified. So a physics-based failure theory for composite materials should adopt the strain or stress information at fiber and matrix scale. Strain invariant failure theory is such a theory that evaluates the failure condition by checking three strain invariants, which have been amplified by micromechanical analysis.

The first invariant is J_1 , can be defined as:

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (1)$$

The second deviatoric strain invariant is defined as:

$$J_2' = \frac{1}{6} \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where, ε_1 , ε_2 and ε_3 are the three principal strains. SIFT adopt von Mises strain instead of the second deviatoric strain invariant,

$$\varepsilon_{vm} = \sqrt{3J_2'} \quad (3)$$

The two quantities are equivalent for evaluating failure. The criteria for SIFT to evaluate failure can be described as follows:

For matrix:

$$J_1^m \geq J_{1,C}^m, \quad \varepsilon_{vm}^m \geq \varepsilon_{vm,C}^m \quad (4)$$

J_1^m and ε_{vm}^m dictate the first strain invariant and von Mises strain in the matrix phase respectively. While J_1^m or ε_{vm}^m exceeds the corresponding critical value $J_{1,C}^m$ or $\varepsilon_{vm,C}^m$, the damage onset appears in the matrix.

For fiber:

$$\varepsilon_{vm}^f \geq \varepsilon_{vm,C}^f \quad (5)$$

ε_{vm}^f and $\varepsilon_{vm,C}^f$ dictate the von Mises strain and the corresponding critical value in the fiber phase respectively. While ε_{vm}^f exceeds $\varepsilon_{vm,C}^f$, the damage onset appears in the fiber phase.

SIFT requires the strain fields at fiber and matrix level. It's tedious and even impossible to develop finite element models including fibers and matrix, so representative volume elements are always utilized to perform micromechanical analysis, based on which, the relations between the nominal external loads and internal strain response can be established.

Consider the representative volume element subjected to an arbitrary state of strain [5]

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{pmatrix}^k - \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \\ \alpha_5 \\ \alpha_6 \end{pmatrix}^k \Delta T = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & M_{14} & M_{15} & M_{16} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} & M_{24} & M_{25} & M_{26} \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} & M_{34} & M_{35} & M_{36} \\ M_{41} & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} & M_{45} & M_{46} \\ M_{51} & M_{52} & M_{53} & M_{54} & M_{55} & M_{56} \\ M_{61} & M_{62} & M_{63} & M_{64} & M_{65} & M_{66} \end{bmatrix}^k \left(\begin{pmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_2 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_3 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_4 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_5 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_6 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\alpha}_1 \\ \bar{\alpha}_2 \\ \bar{\alpha}_3 \\ \bar{\alpha}_4 \\ \bar{\alpha}_5 \\ \bar{\alpha}_6 \end{pmatrix} \Delta T \right) + \begin{pmatrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ A_3 \\ A_4 \\ A_5 \\ A_6 \end{pmatrix}^k \Delta T \quad (6)$$

Where $(\varepsilon_i)^k$ is the strain vector at position k in the micromechanical model for RVE, $(\alpha_i)^k$ is the coefficient of thermal expansion vector of fiber or matrix medium, $[M_{ij}]$ is the strain amplification factors matrix, $(\bar{\varepsilon}_i)$ is the applied external strain for RVE and $(\bar{\alpha}_i)$ is the effective coefficient of thermal expansion matrix, $(A_i)^k$ is the thermal strain amplification vector, ΔT is the difference between curing temperature and operating temperature.

The aim of micromechanical analysis for RVE blocks is to obtain the strain amplification matrix $[M_{ij}]$ and the thermal strain amplification vector (A_i) . The components of $[M_{ij}]$ and (A_i) can easily be determined by performing three dimension finite element analysis for the RVE block with the canonical boundary conditions applied. For example, let $\bar{\varepsilon}_1 = 1$, the other components of $(\bar{\varepsilon}_i)$ are set to zero, also let $\Delta T = 0$. After performing finite element analysis, the first row of the strain amplification matrix can be computed.

3 MICROMECHANICAL MODELS

Generally, there are three kinds of RVE blocks corresponding to three fiber distribution patterns: square, hexagonal and diamond patterns. In this paper, only square fiber distribution pattern is considered. Fig.2 shows a typical finite element mesh for the RVE block with square fiber distribution pattern.

Figure 1: Square, hexagonal and diamond fiber distribution pattern RVE blocks

Figure 2: Finite element mesh for square array representative volume element block

Figure 3: Characteristic points in the representative volume element block

Based on the previous research [5], the selected points for the square fiber distribution pattern are shown in Fig.3. Point F1, F2, F3 and F4, point M1, M2, M3 and M4 locate at the interface of fiber and matrix interface, are used to evaluate the damage onset at the interface. The strains at F1 to F4 are computed using the fiber material properties, while the strains at M1 to M4 are computed using the matrix material properties in the finite element analysis. IF1, IF2 and IS locate at the surface of the RVE block, are used to evaluate the damage onset inside matrix. Point C locates at the center of fiber, is used to evaluate the damage onset inside fiber phase. Different from the references [3,6], the selected points are much less here, because the strain field obtained based on the developed model considering periodical boundary conditions present centrosymmetric features.

4 PERIODICAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

To obtain the strain amplification factor matrix and the thermal strain vector, three dimensional finite element analyses for RVE blocks must be conducted considering the nominal boundary conditions shown in Table.1. How to apply such boundary conditions is quite important for the determination of the strain amplification factor matrix and the thermal strain vector. Several researchers adopt the displacement boundary conditions assuming that the RVE boundary lines keep still straight after deformation [5,6,7]. In reality, a RVE is a part of the material system, the deformation mode of a RVE must be influenced by the neighbouring RVEs, to properly reflect the compatibility of deformation and stress continuity(Fig.5), it's better to apply periodical boundary conditions to the RVE models. In this paper, efforts are taken to apply periodical boundary conditions to the RVE models by using coupled equations method [9].

Loading direction	Boundary conditions
1-1	$\bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = \bar{\gamma}_{12} = \bar{\gamma}_{13} = \bar{\gamma}_{23} = 0, \Delta T = 0$
2-2	$\bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = \bar{\gamma}_{12} = \bar{\gamma}_{13} = \bar{\gamma}_{23} = 0, \Delta T = 0$
3-3	$\bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = \bar{\gamma}_{12} = \bar{\gamma}_{13} = \bar{\gamma}_{23} = 0, \Delta T = 0$
1-2	$\bar{\gamma}_{12} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = \bar{\gamma}_{13} = \bar{\gamma}_{23} = 0, \Delta T = 0$
1-3	$\bar{\gamma}_{13} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = \bar{\gamma}_{12} = \bar{\gamma}_{23} = 0, \Delta T = 0$
2-3	$\bar{\gamma}_{23} = 1, \bar{\varepsilon}_{11} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{22} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{33} = \bar{\gamma}_{12} = \bar{\gamma}_{13} = 0, \Delta T = 0$

Table 1: Boundary conditions for RVE analysis

See the cubic RVE block with side length L shown in Fig.4, three axes are defined as 1,2 and 3 respectively, the boundary condition for every surface can be expressed as functions of the displacement vector U :

$$U(x_1, x_2, 0) - U_3 = U(x_1, x_2, L) \quad (7)$$

$$U(x_1, 0, x_3) - U_2 = U(x_1, L, x_3) \quad (8)$$

$$U(0, x_2, x_3) - U_1 = U(L, x_2, x_3) \quad (9)$$

Where U_1, U_2 and U_3 are dependent on the loading conditions. For example, while the cubic RVE block is subjected to tension loading at the direction 3, we have $U_3=(0,0, \varepsilon L)$, $U_1=(u_1,0,0)$, $U_2=(0, u_2,0)$, where ε is the engineering strain, u_1 and u_2 can be computed through the following equations, i.e. the resultant force at the surfaces paralleling to direction 3 equal to zero.

$$\int_{\Omega} T_1 d\Omega = 0, x_1 = L, \int_{\Omega} T_2 d\Omega = 0, x_2 = L \quad (10)$$

Where T_1 and T_2 are the normal resultant force at the face $x_1 = L$ and $x_2 = L$, respectively.

In the finite element analysis, the periodical boundary conditions can be realized by establishing coupled constraint equations on the node pairs at corresponding positions in parallel faces.

Figure 4: Sketch for a cubic block with Cartesian coordinates

Figure5: Sketch for the deformation modes of blocks considering periodical boundary conditions

5 EXAMPLES FOR DETERMINATION OF STRAIN AMPLIFIATION FACTORS AND THERMAL STRAIN VECTORS

In this section, examples are given to present the deformation contours and corresponding matrix for a T300 fiber/bismaleimide resin composite with the fiber volume fraction 63%.The material properties for T300 fiber and bismaleimide resin are shown in Table 2. Procedures are completed according to the methods introduced in the above sections, strain contours of the RVE are shown in Fig. 6 to Fig.10. Note that, the strain distributions of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state at direction 2-2 and direction 3-3 are equivalent, also the strain distributions of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state at direction 1-2 and direction 1-3 are equivalent. So, only the strain distributions for loading at 2-2 and 1-2 direction are presented. Moreover, due to the limitation of space, strain amplification factors of the characteristic points at the interface of fiber and matrix are provided only considering fiber material properties, as can be seen from Equation 11 to Equation 18.The thermal strain vectors of the characteristic points for fiber and matrix are presented in Table 3 and Table 4.

Material property	T300 fiber	Bismaleimide resin
E_{11} (GPa)	221	
E_{22} (GPa)	13.8	3.12
E_{33} (GPa)	13.8	
G_{12} (GPa)	8.97	
G_{13} (GPa)	8.97	1.2
G_{23} (GPa)	4.83	
ν_{12}	0.20	
ν_{13}	0.20	0.3
ν_{23}	0.25	
α_{11} ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$)	-4.1×10^{-7}	
α_{22} ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$)	1.0×10^{-5}	4.9×10^{-5}
α_{33} ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$)	1.0×10^{-5}	

Table 2: Material properties of the T300 fiber and bismaleimide resin[10]

Figure 6: Strain distribution of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state in direction 1-1

Figure 7: Strain distribution of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state in direction 2-2

Figure 8: Strain distribution of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state in direction 1-2

Figure 9: Strain distribution of the RVE subjected to unit macro strain state in direction 2-3

Figure 10: Strain distribution of the RVE subjected to temperature difference ΔT

$$M_{IF1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.418 & 2.982 & -0.624 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.179 & -0.343 & 0.588 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.874 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.365 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2.303 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$M_{IF2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.179 & 0.588 & -0.343 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.418 & -0.624 & 2.982 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.365 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.874 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2.303 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$M_{IS} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.272 & 1.071 & -0.0022 & 0 & 0 & 0.0015 \\ -0.272 & -0.0022 & 1.071 & 0 & 0 & 0.0015 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.682 & 0.019 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.019 & 1.682 & 0 \\ -0.0016 & 0.0071 & 0.0071 & 0 & 0 & 2.173 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$M_C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.205 & 0.763 & -0.294 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.205 & -0.294 & 0.763 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.481 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.481 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.417 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$M_{F1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.22 & 0.807 & -0.198 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.193 & -0.066 & 0.429 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.682 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.481 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.629 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$M_{F2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.202 & 0.541 & -0.091 & 0 & 0 & 0.044 \\ -0.202 & -0.091 & 0.541 & 0 & 0 & 0.044 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.459 & 0.122 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.122 & 0.459 & 0 \\ -0.02 & 0.087 & 0.087 & 0 & 0 & 0.617 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$M_{F3} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.193 & 0.43 & -0.066 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.22 & -0.198 & 0.807 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.35 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.682 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.629 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$M_{F4} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.013 & -0.013 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.202 & 0.541 & -0.091 & 0 & 0 & -0.044 \\ -0.202 & -0.091 & 0.541 & 0 & 0 & -0.044 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.459 & -0.122 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.122 & 0.459 & 0 \\ 0.020 & -0.087 & -0.087 & 0 & 0 & 0.617 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Thermal strain vector	IF1 ($\times 10^{-6}$)	IS($\times 10^{-6}$)	IF2($\times 10^{-6}$)	M1($\times 10^{-6}$)	M2($\times 10^{-6}$)	M3($\times 10^{-6}$)	M4($\times 10^{-6}$)
A ₁	7834	7834	7834	7834	7834	7834	7834
A ₂	-12470	37.61	8035	-12120	297.3	6881	297.2
A ₃	8035	37.73	-12470	6882	297.1	-12110	297.2
A ₄	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A ₅	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
A ₆	0	0	0	0	9806	0	0

Table 3: Thermal strain vector for matrix phase

Thermal strain vector	C($\times 10^{-6}$)	F1($\times 10^{-6}$)	F2($\times 10^{-6}$)	F3($\times 10^{-6}$)	F4($\times 10^{-6}$)
A ₁	7834	-71.39	-71.39	-71.39	-71.39
A ₂	5856	-1742	-196.6	640.0E-04	-196.6
A ₃	5856	641.1	-196.6	-1738	-196.6
A ₄	0	0	0	0	0
A ₅	0	0	0	0	0
A ₆	0	0	-1687	0	1687

Table 4: Thermal strain vector for fiber phase

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, efforts are taken to determine the strain amplification factors and the thermal strain vectors for strain invariant failure theory through performing finite element analysis for RVE blocks considering periodical boundary conditions. The boundary conditions are introduced through a coupled equation method by establishing coupled constraint equations on the node pairs at corresponding positions in parallel faces. At last, numerical examples are presented to show the deformation modes and strain distribution contours of typical RVEs subjected to unit macro strains. It must be mentioned that the deformation modes of RVE models considering periodical boundary conditions subjected to shear loading and temperature difference present obvious curved features at the surface, which is different from the models with simplified displacement boundary conditions and may be more reasonable.

REFERENCES

- [1] Liu, K.S, S.W. Tsai, A progressive quadratic failure criterion for a laminate. *Composites Science and Technology*, 1998, 58(7):1023-1032

- [2] Gosse Jon H, Christensen Stephen. Strain invariant failure criteria for polymers in composite materials. *AIAA-2001-1184*.
- [3] Tay, T.E., et al., Damage progression by the element-failure method (EFM) and strain invariant failure theory (SIFT). *Composites Science and Technology*, 2005.65(6): p. 935-944.
- [4] Yudhanto.A. Effects of microechnical factors in the strain invariant failure theory for composites, *ME Thesis, National University of Singapore*, Sinapore,2005.
- [5] David L.Buchanan, Jonathan H. Gosse, Jeffrey A. Wollschager etc. Micromechanical enhancement of the macroscopic strain state for advance composite materials. *Composite science and technology* 69, 2009, pp. 1974-1978.
- [6] T.E.Tay, G. Liu, A. Yudhanto and V.B.C.Tan. A micro-macro approach to modelling progressive damage in composite structures. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*,Vol.17,2008.
- [7] T.E.Tay, S.H.N Tan, V.B.C. Tan and J.H.Gosse. Damage progression by the element-failure method(EFM) and strain invariant failure theory(SIFT). *Composite science and technology* 65, 2005, pp. 935-944.
- [8] Pipes, R.B. and J.H. Gosse, An onset theory for irreversible deformation in composite materials. *ICCM-17, the 17th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Edinburgh, UK, 27-31 Jul 2009.
- [9] Xia Zi-hui, Zou Chu-wei, Yong Qiao-ling, et al. On selection of repeated unit cell model and application of unified periodic boundary conditions in micro-mechanical analysis of composites. *International Journal of Solid & Structure*, 2006, 43(2): 266-278
- [10] Chamis CC, Murthy PLN, Minnetyan L. Progressive fracture in composite structures. *Composite materials: fatigue and fracture*, ASTM STP 1285. American Society for Testing Materials,1997;6:70–84.